

are boundary spanning functions between business organizations and consumers. 'A consumer centric product concept in combination with a psychological carrier system in the form of a mighty brand, these are promising ingredients for the magic formula of marketing success, particularly when paired with the extra sparkle of creativity.' (Schroiff, 2007, P.105) To launch a branded electric car, one needs to really understand what the consumer product proposition is while understanding at the same time that the brand is the psychological carrier system for this product proposition (e.g. Aaker, 2004; Arnold, 2007; Esch, 2004; Keller, 2002). One needs to understand how the proposition and the brand interact and whether they really fit (Van Hamersveld & De Bont, 2007).

The purpose of the present study is to investigate how adding an electric car model (a new product proposition) to the product line of existing car brands, with existing brand personalities and experiences, affects the perception and responses to these brands and their personalities and experiences. We also study how the brand characteristics affect the acceptance of an electric model extension. Moreover, the study investigates the effect of different types of car designs for electric vehicles on these brand perceptions. The present paper describes the pretest stages of this study in which car brands for the main study are selected and various design formats are developed, and it briefly presents the set-up of the main study in which the interaction between existing car brand personalities and experiences and emotionally designed electric variants will be studied.

BRAND PERSONALITY AND BRAND EXPERIENCE

Strong and differentiated brands significantly enhance company performance (Colluci, Montaguti & Lago, 2008; Madden, Fehle & Fournier, 2006; Warlop, Ratneshwar, & Van Osselaer, 2005). Selecting the right product innovation for the right brand and improving brand equity is one of the challenges for introducing the electric car. Brand equity is the current and future potential value that has been created by means of branding (Biel, 1993). Brand identity and brand image are important cornerstones

of brand equity. Brand personality forms a major component of brand identity, which is defined as a brand's meaning, put forward by the firm (Kapferer, 2008). Brand image is the consumers' perception and interpretation of this brand personality (De Pelsmacker, Geuens, & Van den Bergh, 2007). 'Brand Personality is the set of human personality traits that are both applicable to and relevant for brands' (Azoulay & Kapferer, 2003, pp. 151). The work of Aaker (1997) inspired the majority of the research on brand personality to date. His scale which incorporates 5 broad dimensions has been used as a brand personality measure in many studies (Aaker, 1997; Aaker, 1999; Aaker, Benet, Matinez & Garolera, 2001; Kim, Han & Park, 2001). One of the major criticisms on the Aaker scale is that it is a mixture of personality and brand image dimensions. In recent research, Geuens, Weijters and De Wulf (2009) have developed a scale that only includes personality dimensions and is therefore a better representation of the brand personality concept. The scale consists of five factors that show an affinity with the Big Five human personality dimensions: Responsibility, Activity, Aggressiveness, Simplicity and Emotionality. Extensive quantitative research proved that the scale is reliable for between-brand-between-category comparisons, for between-brand-within-category comparisons and for between-respondent comparisons. Responsibility is measured by means of three items: down to earth, stable and responsible. Activity consists of three items: active, dynamic and innovative. Aggressiveness contains two items: aggressive and bold. Simplicity is measured by two items: ordinary and simple. Emotionality consists of two items: romantic and sentimental.

A brand's personality may be inferred from people's association with the brand, from product attributes, from category associations, from the brand name or from brand communications. But also brand experience is a major input for this inference. Brakus, Schmitt and Zhang (2008) showed that brand experience affects consumer satisfaction and loyalty through brand personality associations. Positive brand experience not only affects past satisfaction judgments but also future directed use intentions (Mittal and Kamakura 2001; Oliver, 1997; Reicheld 1996). Brakus, Schmitt and Zarantonello (2008),

conceptualize brand experience as subjective consumer responses that are evoked by specific brand-related experiential attributes. They demonstrate that brand experience comprises four dimensions: sensory, affective, intellectual and behavioural, which are differentially evoked by various brands. Three sensory items (this brand makes a strong impression on my visual sense or other sense; I find this brand interesting in a sensory way; this brand does not appeal to my senses) constitute the first dimension. Three affective items form the second dimension: this brand induces feelings and sentiments; this brand is an emotional brand; I do have strong emotions for this brand. Three items define the behavioural component: I engage in physical actions and behaviours when I use this brand; this brand results in bodily experiences; this brand is not action oriented. The three remaining items form the intellectual dimension: I engage a lot in thinking when I encounter this brand; this brand does not make me think; this brand stimulates my curiosity and problem solving. The present paper is a first step in investigating the impact of existing brand experience and brand personality on the adoption intention of the electric car introduced by these brands, using the constructs and measures proposed by Geuens et al. (2009) and Brakus et al. (2008).

THE ELECTRIC CAR AS A PRODUCT

Design is an unequivocal source of differentiation and has become a key element for branding, not only because aesthetically pleasing products and services better compete for consumers' short attention span (Berkowitz 1987, Page and Herr, 2002), but also because design may serve as a cohesive factor for all elements that configure a brand's personality and experience. Getting people to purchase electric cars will be as much about making them feel good about those cars as about giving them hard facts and figures on the improvements in emissions and fuel consumption (Motavelli, 2000). Earlier research revealed that the product propositions 'sustainability' and 'ecological responsibility' are not enough to convince a large target group. Lane and Potter (2007) conclude that, although consumers

mention sustainability issues as a major consumer concern, the attitude-behaviour gap reveals that consumer concern for environmental impact does not often translate into behavioural change. By understanding how people feel about their cars and about electric cars, we can find out what is necessary to make the transition from today's car culture to a more socially and environmentally 'responsible' transportation culture (Sheller, 2000). Car markets and driving decisions are not simply rational economic choices, but are as much about aesthetic, emotional, and sensory responses. Norman (2004) claims that psychological aspects of ergonomics have become increasingly important in the pursuit of products that are not only safe and efficient, but also pleasurable and arousing to use. Emotions powerfully influence many of our product and brand choices (Penn, 2007). A large-scale quantitative study into the determinants of electric car adoption intention in Belgium, applying an extended version of the Theory of Planned Behaviour, revealed that emotional feelings towards using an electric vehicle are more important determinants of the adoption intention than attitudes, the subjective norm or perceived behavioural control factors (Moons and De Pelsmacker, 2011). Norman (2004) argues that the emotional reaction to design and/or to an existing or new product may be more critical to a product's success than its practical elements. These emotions are related to the complex brain structure with three emotional processing levels (Mc Clean, 1990): visceral, behavioral and reflective. The first level, i.e. visceral affect, is perception-based and relates to visceral aspects that are related to product appearance. 'To experience a new car is to allow a series of sensual triggers to be pulled. One takes in the body-form; one eyes the exterior details; one touches parts of the trim...' As Miller (2001, p.24) suggests, 'it is this highly visceral relationship between bodies of people and bodies of cars that forces us to acknowledge the humanity of the car in the first place'. The second level, i.e. behavioral emotion, is expectation-based and corresponds with behavioral aspects that have to do with the pleasure and effectiveness of use. 'The cabin of a car and the

seats in particular, may not seem to be the sexiest element of the getting-to-know-you experience. Actually that's precisely what they are. As soon as you slide into the front seat, the car is yours; and the car has got you...just sitting in it is a real pleasure. What I refer to as 'automotive emotions' - the 'thrill' of driving, the 'joy' of the road, the 'passion' of the collector, the 'feeling' of the car interior - are not simply lexicons of the advertising imaginary' (Sheller, 2001, p.17).

The third level i.e. reflective emotion is intellectually based and corresponds with reflective dimensions that are concerned with self-image, personal satisfaction and memories. As Maxwell (2001, p. 217) argues, 'meanings of car use are fundamentally embedded in social relations of everyday life, and... an understanding of the interrelationships between the plural ethical discourses associated with car use, provides an alternative means of understanding the gap between attitudes and behaviour'.

Since different emotional reactions are being evoked by products, It is vital to better understand how people relate to (new) products based on these different emotional processing and experience levels.

Experience refers to an individual's stream of perceptions, interpretations of those perceptions, and resulting emotions during encounter with a system. The core of user experience will be the actual experience of usage. This does not cover all relevant user experience concerns. People can have indirect experience before their first encounter, through expectations formed from existing experience of related technologies (the current car), brand, advertisements, presentations, demonstrations, and the opinion of others. For the moment, measuring actual usage experiences of a wide variety of branded electric cars is impossible, because only a small proportion of the large brands already introduced electric cars. The present study can thus not reach any further than exploring the anticipated user experience that might be provoked by the manipulation of product aspects of branded electric cars.

The aim of the present study is to test three types of designs of an electric car model for existing brands, representing Norman's (2004) three emotional

experience levels, and to investigate to what extent these anticipated emotions affect brand personality, brand experience, brand attitude and electric car adoption intention, and whether this depends on existing car brand personalities and experiences.

LOOKING FOR A WAY TO INTEGRATE EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES INTO A BRANDED ELECTRIC CAR

Anticipated emotional experiences are the result of concrete and abstract car attributes that should be made actionable. Traditional models such as the Quality function deployment model (Clausing, 1994) and the means - end model of quality (Zeithaml, 1988) argue that consumer attributes can be grouped into a hierarchy of higher order abstract attributes and lower level concrete attributes. Consumers do not always relate abstract to concrete attributes. They seem to be unable to explain how a concrete product reflects an abstract attribute. One of the challenges is to translate abstract attributes into concrete and specific attributes by means of design elements. One of the aims of this study is thus also to design branded electric car concepts that evoke different types of emotions. The result of this conceptual product design (concept boards) will be tested in further experimental research to investigate how different product experience features can evoke different emotional processing reactions, how these different types of products (visceral, behavioural, reflective) interact with existing brand personalities and experience, and how they are related to the adoption intention of the electric car

SETTING UP AN EXPERIMENT TO INVESTIGATE THE INTERACTION BETWEEN CAR BRAND PERSONALITY AND EXPERIENCE AND CAR DESIGN

The most adequate research technique for our research questions is setting up an experiment. By carefully selecting car brands and emotional electric car types, we can identify the impact of brand

personalities and emotional product types on brand attitude, adoption intention, brand personality, and brand experience for an electric variant of existing car brands. The present paper focus on a series of pretests in order to select a set of appropriate car brands and to prepare concepts of electric car types.

First we conducted a qualitative study to come up with a workable list of car brands. The second step aimed at describing these car brands in terms of brand personalities and brand experiences. The result of this exercise was a shortlist of three car brands that varied substantially in terms of brand personalities and brand experiences. The personalities and experiences associated with these brands were then further studied in a qualitative study in the third step. The fourth step was a co-creation exercise. This step led us to generate product features that elicit anticipated emotions at the three product processing levels. These features were analyzed and a selection was made for a design briefing. On the basis of this briefing, in the fifth step, twelve concept cards were developed. In the sixth step, these concept cards are tested on their relevance for studying the aimed experience manipulations. In the final step, documented in this paper, the main experiment is introduced.

Step 1: generating the brand list

The aim of the first qualitative study was to generate a list of relevant car brands to take along in our study.

Procedure and sample

From the internet, literature and a small brainstorm with three colleagues from Artesis University College, all possible car brands were listed and 39 brands that produce family cars were selected. Twelve respondents were selected to participate in an individual interview. The sample consisted of different age categories, as many male as female respondents, and all of them were driving a family car. The last feature was taking into account because people driving more special cars (roadsters, small cars, SUV's) might have a different opinion on the car types we want to consider in further research. An earlier study (Moons and De Pelsmacker, 2011) revealed a link between owning a

family car and the intention to adopt an electric car. So we will focus on this car segment.

Task and results

The respondents were asked to categorize the brands (written down on small cards) on their personality, using the five personality items as proposed by Geuens et al. (2009): responsible, active, aggressive, simple, and emotional. Twelve brands that were associated most often with only one personality trait were selected for further research: Alfa, Audi, BMW, Ford, Mercedes, Nissan, Opel, Renault, Saab, Toyota, Volkswagen, Volvo.

Step 2: reduction of the brand list

The purpose of the second step was to narrow down the list of twelve brands to a list of three car brands that were as different as possible with respect to their brand personality and brand experience for further use in the main experiment.

Procedure and sample

An online questionnaire was sent to a sample of 100 family car drivers. Thirty eight respondents, 45% male completed the questionnaire. The sample consists of respondents of different age brackets: 18-25 (11%), 25-35 (18%), 35-45 (26%), 45-65 (42%), >65 (3%).

Questionnaire

In order not to complicate this stage of the test, the search for the most suitable brands to take along in further research, we modified the scales proposed by Geuens et al. (2009) and Brakus et al. (2008). Instead of using seven-point Likert scales to measure brand personality and experience, only a categorization of the most suitable and the least suitable dimension of brand personality and brand experience was asked for. For each of the 12 car brands that remained from the first step of the research the respondents were asked which of the five personality traits suited the most and which one the least to the brand: responsible, active, aggressive, simple, emotional. The same was done for the four brand experience dimensions: sensitive, affective, behavioural, reflective.

Results:

The three most differentiated brands, taking brand personalities and brand experiences into account, were: SAAB, BMW and TOYOTA. Saab is most

frequently and more often than the other brands in the list associated with an emotional brand personality (35%) and with sensitive (36%) and affective (32%) brand experience dimensions. At the same time, Saab is least associated with the brand personality dimension 'simple' (53%) and with reflective experiences (47%). BMW is most strongly associated with the brand personality dimension 'aggressive' (49%) and as well with affective (41%) as behavioural (41%) brand experience dimensions. BMW is least associated with the brand personality characteristics 'simple' (73%) and with reflective experiences (47%). Toyota is strongly associated with simple (58%). It is least associated with aggressive (46%). It has not a very pronounced brand experience profile. Consequently, the development of the design stimuli will be based on the SAAB, BMW and TOYOTA brands.

Step 3: relating selected brands to electric mobility

Step 3 is a qualitative diagnostic check of the results of the previous quantitative study. We explored to what extent the selected brands were different with respect to their suitability for an electric car variant, and to what extent we could expect the brand personality and the brand experience to change when we add the product attribute 'electric'.

Method and procedure

For each brand, three group discussions were organized (a total of 9 discussions), each consisting of 5 participants, all of them master students in product development. Creative and projective techniques were set up to make it easier to explore the more abstract concepts of brand personality and brand experience. Each group started with exploring the brand personality and the evoked brand experience of one of the selected brands (either SAAB, BMW or TOYOTA). First they spontaneously discussed what the brand meant to them. Then they were allowed to screen brand communications on the internet and in magazines. After this introduction phase, projective techniques were used to make it easier to communicate on relatively abstract product attributes. The groups discussed about the kind of person the car brand would be, with which animal they associated the car brand, and about the planet the car brand should be on. To conclude, they were

asked to compose a collage (moodboard) about the brand. The same exercise was done for the 'electric' variant of the brand.

Results

Saab is described as a classy, well designed brand (well dressed man) that is technologically advanced (intelligent, sensitive, up to date). It is an emotional brand (a proud deer with emotional big eyes; it isn't just a car that brings you from point A to point B, but it delivers a good feeling; it de-stresses you; it takes you through great nature...). Saab is suitable for a family (the animal cares about its family), and 'nature' and 'green' are associated with it. The attribute 'electric' gives the brand a more female touch and makes it even more sensitive (it will be silent in the car, listening to the music will even be better, it will even look more beautiful, more trendy...). It also makes the brand more emotional (caring, loving). It suits to SAAB as SAAB already stands for an environmentally caring brand.

BMW is an active, sporty, even aggressive brand (a poema, a panter a tiger, a carnivor). It is described as strong, sharp and masculine. The BMW planet is rather technical (collage with watches, planes), luxury (people playing Polo, golf) and active (skiing, sailing). In the moodboard, participants also included a lot of show-off elements. When adding the attribute 'electric', the brand becomes more feminine, softer, more casual, but also more responsible and more reflective. Respondents believe in the effort that the BMW technology promises for saving the environment, but they don't see the electric car fit with the brand in the near future. Toyota is described as a simple brand that does not have a typical character. It is a bit sporty and it is a person's rational choice (a simple, common person, plays football, a dog, you buy a Toyota because it is ok, and that's the one you can afford,). Toyota already tries to be ecologically friendly. The attribute 'electric' would change its image slightly in a more technologically advanced brand. It will make the brand more advanced and trendier while keeping its rational and responsible brand associations.

The results of this qualitative study largely confirm the brand personalities we found in the previous step. Moreover, adding the attribute 'electric' appears to have a differential effect on the three

brands. ‘Electric’ seems to match best with Saab and Toyota and less with BMW, and affects brand personalities differently. Steps 2 and 3 lead to the conclusion that the three brands are sufficiently different in terms of brand personality, brand experience and fit with the attribute ‘electric’ to warrant their inclusion in the main experiment.

Step 4: determining product features to elicit the product experience levels

Now that the actual brand personalities and brand experiences were established for each brand, the next question was how to evoke the three different emotional brand experiences as suggested by Norman (2004) by manipulating the product itself, i.e. the design of the car. In this fourth step we thus try to establish which product features can evoke an anticipated emotional experience at the three product processing levels: visceral, behavioral and reflective.

Method and procedure

Brainstorming sessions were organized to evoke product attributes for an electric car variant at the different emotional processing levels. Groups of between 6 and 10 participants (all postgraduate students) were formed. The same persons who took part in the qualitative brand exercise in step 3 were now brainstorming on the same brand, but not necessary in the same group composition as for the earlier exercise. Two groups worked on each of the three car brands, so we had six brainstorm sessions to study possible features at the three experience levels. Different tools were introduced to stimulate the creative process. First the group had to reformulate the questions: how can we add more experience to the brand (either Saab, BMW, Toyota) by means of product features. How can we add more visceral, behavioral and reflective emotions to the brand (either, Saab, BMW or Toyota) by means of product features? A ‘divergent thinking exercise’ was introduced to open up the mind of the respondents. The features of the existing brand could be substituted by other features, also from other product categories. Features could be combined, restructured, adapted, resized, or eliminated. The product could be given a new destiny, a new advantage... Elements of the world of animals and nature could be used as inspiration. Every feature they found could be re-associated with another

possible feature. This phase resulted in between 100 and 195 items for each group. Next, these items were assigned to four categories on the basis of two dimensions: which of the items are actionable and which of the items are breakthrough versus evolutionary (Table 1).

	actionable	not actionable
breakthrough	Ideas for the middle term	Ideas for the far future
evolutionary	Ideas for the near future	Ideas to throw away

Table 1. Categorization of the design ideas

We then focused on actionable ideas for the near future. In the last phase of this exercise the groups made a table of product features that give the brands (Saab, BMW, Toyota) a more visceral, behavioral or reflective experience.

Results

For each anticipated product experience level, three product features were selected for further elaboration (Table 2). These were selected on the frequency with which they were mentioned and on their categorization as original and workable in the near future. Because this phase in the research has to result into a design briefing to create concept cards, the possibility to visualize the items was taken into account as well.

visceral	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Attractive wheels 2. Light bulbs like seducing eyes 3. Inviting seats that seem to carry and support your body
behavioural	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Finger touch to open the door 2. Smart car/smart phone interaction 3. Adaptable driving possibility: sporty, city, sight seeing

reflective	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dashboard information on consumption, ecological footprint, loading possibilities 2. Showing that you're driving electric (outside labeling) 3. Possible combination with other ecological transport
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Table 2. selected ideas at the three anticipated product experience levels.

Step 5: Creation of concept cards

The overall results of the brainstorm session in the previous step were used as input to create four concept cards for each electric car brand. Based on an earlier quantitative study (Moons and De Pelsmacker, 2011) that showed that people driving a family car are more likely to adopt an electric car, we chose a family car model for each brand. For Saab, the concept cards are based on the Saab 9.3, for BMW on the BMW3 and for Toyota on the Avensis. Besides the basic concept cards for each brand that served as control conditions, each electric car brand sketch was manipulated three times, in accordance with each of the three emotional product experience levels and based on the results of the brainstorming sessions. The basic template was the same for the three manipulated experience conditions and the representation of the three car brands was kept under control as well (same colors, no background, same perspective, same size,...). The sketches explicitly show the car brand (logo, typical car design) and make clear that it is about electric cars.

Results

The 12 sketches are currently being developed. A preliminary example is given below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Preliminary example of concept cards

Step 6: Testing and refining the concept cards

Once the concept cards will be finished an online quantitative study will be set up to test the cards on whether the designs clearly convey the intended experience levels. On the basis of the results of this study, some of the cards will probably need to be partly redesigned as to develop the right stimuli for the next step in our study.

Step 7: Main experiment

In order to test the interaction between existing brand personalities and experiences on the one hand, and the type of design on the other, a quantitative online experiment will be conducted. A between-subjects 3x4 experimental design will be set up as represented in Table 3. Investigating which product manipulations lead to differential effects on brand personalities, experiences, attitudes and adoption intentions for each electrified brand implies the need to know how these brands are perceived initially on the aspects of brand personality, brand experience and adoption intention. Therefore, besides three different design types for each brand, also three control groups will

be used to measure the initial (i.e. not electrified) brand personalities and experiences. The independent variables are thus the product stimulus types (three different design types that evoke different emotions and a control design, as represented by four concept cards) and the car brand (three brands) given in each experimental condition.

Individuals with driving experience with the car brands (not electrified) will be selected (i.e. people who already drove a Saab, a BMW or a Toyota)

	CONTROL	VISCERAL	BEHAVIOURAL	REFLECTIVE
SAAB	n=100	n=100	n=100	n=100
BMW	n=100	n=100	n=100	n=100
TOYOTA	n=100	n=100	n=100	n=100

Table3: 3x4 Between-subjects experimental design

CONCLUSION

The present paper tries to gain consumer insights into creating value by means of a consumer-centered innovation, selecting the right product innovation that fits with existing brand equity. It tries to understand how the proposition of the electric car interacts with the brand personalities and brand experiences of three existing car brands and whether they fit. It further explores the elaboration of product features that might evoke anticipated product experiences at the visceral, behavioral and reflective processing level and the extent to which these different emotional electric car products fit with existing brand personalities and experiences. The result of the pretests reported in the present study is a set of branded electric product propositions that need to be tested in a large sample of potential (electric) car buyers. The core question to be answered is which propositions for which brands will lead to which attitude and intention to adopt an electric car brand variant? Earlier research (Moons and De Pelsmacker, 2011) has shown the importance of emotions in the adoption intention of the electric car. This study

elaborates which product features can appeal to this emotional determinant. Furthermore the study is an exploration of the relationship between marketing and product development. The study tries to fill the gap between research and action in the domain of marketing. The separation between the field of marketing research and marketing action (creating new products) is longstanding (Durgee, 1987). The different orientations of these two fields are combined in this paper. The first three steps and the step to be taken next in the research project is focused on consumer understanding, the brainstorm session (step 4) and the creation phase (step 5) is more action based.

Other crucial questions are: What kind of new exciting offer do we present to the consumer? What are we going to tell him about what the product does? What kind of problem solver does it represent? What do you tell them about the brand as 'icing on the cake'? How will the aspect of 'ecologically friendly' fit into this proposition? These are topics for further research

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